
DRUG ABUSE AS A CORRELATE OF SOCIAL STUDIES ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE AMONG TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS STUDENTS IN DELTA STATE

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated drug abuse as a correlate of social studies academic performance among tertiary institutions students in Delta State. Three hypotheses and three research questions were developed and put to the test. Research on correlation was used in this study. 249 undergraduate Social Studies students from Delta State's tertiary institutions made up the study's population. There are 249 social studies students across all institutions that make up the study's sample. Student performance ratings and a validated questionnaire were the study's instruments. Measurement and evaluation experts validated the questionnaire. The Cronbach Alpha was applied in the computation of the instrument's reliability, yielding a reliability value of 0.83. Simple Correlation and Linear regression were used to analyze the study's data. The results of the analysis showed that Drug abuse significantly correlates with academic performance of Social Studies students in tertiary institutions in Delta State. Drug abuse significantly correlates with academic performance of Social Studies students in tertiary institutions in Delta State on the basis of gender and drug abuse significantly correlates with academic performance of Social Studies students in tertiary institutions in Delta State on the basis of location. Based on the findings, it was determined that drug abuse and social studies students' performance at Delta State's tertiary institutions are related. Among the recommendations given in light of the result was that the Ministry of Education should provide instructors more training in behaviour management. School administrators should also get training in order to provide them with the necessary information and abilities to handle widespread disturbance in their schools. This training should be comprehensive and represent a change from the National Centre for Education Resource Development's ad hoc sessions.

Keywords: Drug Abuse, Academic Performance, Social Studies

INTRODUCTION

Nigeria's educational system comprises three main sectors, which include primary and secondary education and tertiary education, which usually lasts for a period of four to six years, depending on one's academic discipline of study. The tertiary institution sector consists of universities, polytechnics, and colleges of education. The entire tertiary institution, be it a university or non-university, offers academic opportunities for students to study any course of their choice (FRN, 2014).

The tertiary education institutions are saddled with the responsibility of producing quality graduates who will become great leaders and workers for the country's labour sectors. The main criterion for graduating students into the labour market is successful academic performance. Busari (2020) stated that academic performance is the display of knowledge attained or skills developed in a school subject. Dimbisso (2019) explained that academic performance is how learners handle their studies as well as how they achieve the various tasks given to them by their teachers at a particular time or academic session. Academic performance in various subject areas is measured through grades, marks, and scores assigned by teachers. Grades and scores obtained by students represent students' mental ability and scholastic standing.

Academic performance is an indicator of the effectiveness of schools, an indicator of the quality of education, and a determinant of the level of academic success of students in particular and the nation in general (Lewin, *et al.*, 2017). An individual's career placement is also influenced by their academic performance. Better education provides students with more career options and better compensation potential due to their superior academic performance. If students do poorly academically, there may be unfavourable effects on instructors, students, and society as large. (Tshewang, 2015). Academic performance by numerous students in both public and private institutions of higher learning has gained significant attention from most researchers in the field of education. Many research efforts have been directed towards identifying the factors responsible for the unsatisfactory academic performance of students. Adekunle and Femi-Adeoye (2016) ascertained that socio-demographic factors like students' attitudes, interests, gender, parent socioeconomic status, and learning habits are some factors affecting students' academic performance. However, the researcher in this present study believed that drug abuse might also be a factor affecting the academic performance of students.

Drug abuse has a number of negative social, economic, psychological, cultural, physical, moral, and health effects that may cause users to become impoverished, disabled, struggle to integrate into society, or even pass away. Chinkere and Mayowa (2019) emphasised that drugs may lead to traumatic effects that can result in death or impairment at a very early age, in addition to the chronic ailments that frequent drinkers can develop over many years. According to their research, drug use accounts for 20–30% of all oesophagus, liver, and cirrhosis cases worldwide, as well as murder, epilepsy, and auto accidents. Ajayi and Ekundayo (2018) state that drug misuse could result in a number of effects, which include elevated rates of criminal activity, engagement in cult activities, mental health issues, low self-esteem, subpar academic achievement, physical harm, social exclusion, and embarrassment to one's family. Furthermore, Ojikutu (2020) pointed out that using stimulants to keep up at night, such as kola nuts, strong coffee, and other drugs, might result in drug addiction and dependence. In contrast to what the students expected, this has a detrimental impact on their health and leads to low performance among students.

The World Health Organisation (WHO, 2019) reported that the risk of exposure to drug abuse has become one of the factors that influences the development of the burden of disease. Additionally, the report noted that adolescent behaviour can account for a third of the disease burden in adults. The World Health Organisation (2019) highlighted that since young individuals have lower muscle mass than adults, medicines may have more rapid and severe effects on them. According to Oshodi et al. (2020), brain tiredness syndrome—a disorder that is especially common among West African students—is associated with high caffeine use. Poor study absorption, head and neck somatic symptoms, and visual abnormalities are the hallmarks of this illness. Furthermore, Adamson et al. (2020) noted that younger people are beginning to use drugs and raised concern about the rising trend of drug use among teenagers. Early drug use is linked to more serious addiction, criminal activity, delinquency, and behavioural and psychological issues.

There are various reasons why students abuse drugs, including social pressure influenced by mass media, peer group influence, lack of parental care and supervision, the need for fun and happiness, the availability of drugs, access to money to purchase drugs, and family background. According to Amadi and Akpelu (2018), students often turn to drugs due to boredom, stress, depression, curiosity, weight loss, low self-esteem, the desire for enhanced experiences, and peer pressure. Chukwu et al. (2017) found that many students abuse drugs to relieve stress, alleviate boredom, boost low self-esteem, and enhance their experiences. Ezeudu (2020) discussed the impact of school location, distinguishing between urban and rural settings, on social studies education and the psychosocial influences affecting teachers and students. He noted that urban students generally perform better academically than their rural counterparts and that drug abuse is more prevalent among rural students.

This disparity is attributed to the organised environment and diverse amenities in urban areas compared to rural settings. Ezeudu (2020) also reported that students in both urban and rural areas engage in drug abuse and experience bullying similarly. However, his findings indicated that the majority of Social Studies students who abuse drugs and experience bullying are located in major urban centres rather than rural areas. Considering these circumstances, it is imperative to explore the impact of drug abuse on the academic performance of students. This discussion suggests that drug abuse can have either negative or positive impacts on students' academic performance. Consequently, this study examines what effect drug abuse has on students' performance in Delta State.

Statement of the Problem

A knowledge-driven global economy has heightened the importance of tertiary education for economic competitiveness. Tertiary education is widely acknowledged as a vital factor for economic competitiveness. Tertiary institution students' academic performance is usually expressed in terms of Grade Point Average (GPA). GPA is typically conceptualized as a measure of academic performance. Several studies like Odesa and Ogheneakoke (2022); Atubi (2022) and Obro, *et al.*, (2021) have also revealed that students' academic performances over the years are not very impressive. Unsatisfactory academic performance among students is indeed a thing of great concern to parents, teachers, school management, the government, curriculum designers and the general public, to this effect this study investigated psychological factors that can affect students' academic performance, ranging to such as bullying and drug abuse.

Personal observation and reports also revealed that drug abuse influence students' academic performance in school. However, not many empirical studies have been carried out in recent times to support this assertion, especially in the department of Social Studies of

higher institutions across Delta State. Paucity of empirical studies on the influence of drug abuse on academic performance particularly among Social Studies students in tertiary institution of Delta State was the major concern of this research and necessitated this study; influence of drug abuse on academic performance among tertiary Social Studies students in Delta State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were answered in this study;

1. Does drug abuse correlate with social studies academic performance among tertiary institutions students in delta state?
2. Does drug abuse correlate with social studies academic performance among tertiary institutions students in delta state on the basis of gender?
3. Does drug abuse correlate with social studies academic performance among tertiary institutions students in delta state on the basis of location?

Hypotheses

The study was guided by the following hypotheses;

1. Drug abuse does not significantly correlate with academic performance of Social Studies students in tertiary institutions in Delta State.
2. Drug abuse does not significantly correlate with academic performance of Social Studies students in tertiary institutions in Delta State on the basis of gender.
3. Drug abuse does not significantly correlate with academic performance of Social Studies students in tertiary institutions in Delta State on the basis of location.

Literature review

Theoretical Framework

The theory for this study is social learning theory. Social learning theory is concerned with the relationship between social and environmental factors, and their influence on human behavior. Social learning theory (Bandura, 1977) suggests continuous and reciprocal interaction between the individuals' cognition and behavior exist within the ecological environment where human behavior is developed. According to the proponent of the theory, human behavior is not inborn. Rather it is learned through our socialization process. Individual observational learning is acquired by attention to and retention of activities. Such activities are determined by interpersonal interactions and behaviors of people with whom individuals regularly associate. Modeling is the stage where individuals have strong motivation to deliberately shape their behaviors in accordance with symbolic behaviors of others.

The theory suggests that children learn through modeling, observing and imitating others' behavior. This process becomes a socialization process, leading to the development of habitual response patterns. As children grow, they imitate different models from their social environment, including parents, siblings, and extended family members. People learn good or bad behaviors through observational learning, extracting information from their social world, and making choices that maximize environmental rewards while avoiding negative outcomes. Successful imitation of drug use occurs through attention, retention, motoric reproduction, and reinforcement. The model's performance is stored in memory, and the individual uses this representation to guide their own behavior. Positive outcomes encourage the potential abuser to try the same behavior in similar situations. This theoretical formulation was considered significant in the study since it underscores the importance of observational learning in the

acquisition and sustenance of drug taking behavior. Adolescents who are potential abusers of drugs observe drug taking behavior in people who are significant in their lives such as parents and friends. Based on the outcomes the models experience, the adolescent might choose to imitate the same drug taking behavior.

Drug Abuse and Academic Performance

This section discussed some empirical studies that have been carried out on drugs abuse and academic performance. According to Oghuvbu (2015) research, substance addiction and secondary school academic achievement are correlated. Data from 2860 pupils in 58 schools were gathered for the research, which showed a mean score of 68% for drug addiction and 66% for academic achievement. Additionally, the research discovered a somewhat favourable link, with drug addiction in Delta State, Nigeria, having an impact on 22% of pupils' academic performance. The association between drug misuse in the classroom and academic performance among university students was investigated by Lukkarinen et al. (2016). They found three groups: dropouts, those attending classes, and independent students. In group 2, drugs abuse positively impacted performance. In group 3, students with bullying reasons and independent study skills showed better performance. The findings are relevant for both students and teachers. The research conducted by Fabgenle and Elegbeleye (2018) investigated the effects of drug misuse on the academic achievement of secondary school pupils in Osun State, Nigeria. They collected data from 3,050 students from 61 state-owned schools over three years. The results showed that average drug abuse scores were proportional to examination scores. Amro, et. al., (2015) studied the impact of drug abuse and gender on student performance in college algebra classes. They found that gender was a predictor of performance in face-to-face courses, while neither drug abuse nor gender affected online students' grades. The study found that face-to-face students had higher average grades. Adekunle (2017) study found significant differences in students' performance in the West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE) biology multiple choice test based on drug abuse, gender, and school type among 1450 Secondary School Three students from 20 Ekiti State, Nigeria schools.

Gender and Academic Performance

This section discussed some empirical studies that have been carried out on gender and academic performance. Okoh, Iwuozor, and Odinma's 2017 study found gender differences in chemistry computational problems among senior secondary school students. The study, administered to 400 students, found that male students did not perform significantly better in computational problems compared to female students. This finding is relevant to the current study, which examines gender influence on 3-D organic molecular structures in chemistry. A study by Oludipe (2016) examined the impact of gender on Junior Secondary students' academic performance in basic science using cooperative learning teaching strategies. The study involved 120 students from three selected schools in Ogun State, Nigeria. The results showed no significant difference in academic performance between male and female students at pretest, post-test, and delayed post-test levels. Igboegwu and Okonkwo (2016) examined the impact of gender and school location on students' chemistry performance in Anambra State Secondary Schools. The study involved 1889 students, with 844 males and 1045 females. Results showed a higher, but not statistically significant, gender advantage in chemistry performance. The study also examined the influence of location and education zone on students' conception levels in 3-D organic molecular structure. Onuekwusi (2015) investigated the main and interaction effects of gender and content area on students' performance in chemistry and revealed that gender has no significant influence on the performance while content area does. There was no significant

gender and content area interaction effect. Nnamani and Oyibe (2016) study examined the gender and academic performance of secondary school students in chemistry in Abakaliki, Ebonyi State. The research involved 3,469 students from various secondary schools. The study found that female students had higher mean performance scores than male students. Additionally, male and female students taught chemistry by male teachers had higher mean scores. Female students performed better than male students taught chemistry by male teachers. The study found significant differences in mean performance based on gender.

Location and Academic Performance

Nnenna and Adukwu (2018) conducted a study on the impact of gender and school location on senior secondary school students' performance in biology in Agbani Education Zone, Enugu State. The study involved 328 students from co-education and intact SS3 classes, with a multiple-stage sampling technique. The Biology Performance Test (BAT) was used for data collection. The results showed significant differences in performance scores between male and female students, with urban students achieving higher results. Ashimolowo and Odiachi (2018) conducted a study on bullying activities in rural areas of Delta State, Nigeria. The study involved 70 respondents from seven blocks, with 75.71% being males and 22.29% females. The majority had a secondary school education and were married. Only 25.71% had over 25 years of farming experience. 50% agreed the government should be blamed for the crises.

RESEARCH METHOD

This study utilized a correlational research design to examine the impact of the independent variable, drug abuse, on the dependent variable, academic performance. The study population included all undergraduate Social Studies students in government-owned Colleges of Education and Universities in Delta State, totaling 249 students according to the Academic Record Unit of the respective schools. Due to the relatively small size of the population, the researcher opted to include all 249 students in the study. Thus, the sample size comprised 249 undergraduate Social Studies students in Delta State.

Two instruments used for this study are self-developed Questionnaire titled Drug Abuse and Academic Performance (DAAPQ), and students' past semester results. The validation of the instrument was carried out on the questionnaire which was given to two research experts in the Department of Measurement and Evaluation in Delta State University Abraka to ascertain the face and content validity, before giving the instrument to the research supervisor.

The reliability of instrument was established through a test-retest method. Thus, the instrument was subjected to a pilot test applying the test-retest method for an interval of two weeks to twenty (20) students outside the study area. The data obtained was analyzed using the Pearson Correlation moment with the aid of computer software, Reliability index of 0.75 was obtained for drug abuse scale. This shows the instrument was reliable. A total of 249 copies of the questionnaire was distributed to the respondents by the researcher with the help of four research assistants. The research assistants assisted the respondents in retrieving their questionnaires after they had completed them. A Pearson's Product Moment Correlation was used to answer research questions; linear regression was used to test hypotheses to determine how the variables were related statistically.

Presentation of Results

Research Questions 1: Does drug abuse correlates with social studies academic performance among tertiary institutions students in delta state.

Table 1: Correlation (r) Analysis of drug abuse and academic performance of Social Studies Students

Variables	N	Mean	SD	R	r ²	r ^{2adj}	r ² %	Remark
Drug abuse	249	2.4833	1.04482	.341	.116	.114	11.60	Positive correlation
Academic performance	249	57.62	9.56					

The Pearson Product Moment Correlation (r) value of 0.341 in Table 1 indicated the degree of association between drug abuse and academic performance among Social Studies students in Delta State's tertiary institutions. Drug abuse seems to have positive correlation with academic achievement among Social Studies students in Delta State's postsecondary institutions. The variance in academic performance of Social Studies students at tertiary institutions in Delta State was found to be 11.6% influenced by drug addiction, according to the coefficient of determination (r²) value of .116. Conclusion: There is a positive correlation between drug abuse and academic performance among Social Studies students in Delta State's post-secondary schools.

Research Question 2: Does drug abuse correlate with social studies academic performance among tertiary institution students in delta state on the basis of gender?

Table 2: Multiple Correlation of how drug abuse affects academic performance with regard to gender

Variables	N	Mean	SD	R	R ²	R ^{2adj}	R ² %	Remark
Gender	249	1.61	.48	.922	.850	.848	85.0	Positive relationship
Drug abuse	249	2.48	1.04					
Academic performance	249	57.62	9.56					

Table 2 revealed that R=.922 was the Multiple Correlation of the association moderating influence among academic performance, drug abuse, and gender. This number suggests a positive correlation between gender, drug addiction, and academic achievement. With a coefficient of determination (r²) of .850, it was shown that drug addiction and gender together accounted for 85% of the difference in academic performance among social studies students in Delta State's postsecondary institutions. Thus, it was determined that there is a positive correlation between gender, drug addiction, and academic performance.

Research Question 3: Does drug abuse correlate with social studies academic performance among tertiary institution students in delta state on the basis of location?

Table 3: Correlation (r) Analysis of drug abuse influence on academic performance

Variables	N	Mean	SD	R	r ²	r ^{2adj}	r ² %	Remark
Location	249	36.8111	6.36644	.878	.771	.770	77.1	Positive impact
Drug abuse	249	2.2167	.79885					
Academic performance	249	57.6222	9.56150					

Independent Variable: location, drug abuse.

Dependent Variable: Academic performance

Table 3 showed that the Multiple Correlation (r) value for the association between academic performance, drug addiction, and location was .878, showing a substantial correlation between these factors for Delta State Tertiary Social Studies students enrolled in tertiary institutions. This positive correlation implies that drug addiction and location have an effect on academic achievement. The location and drug misuse of these kids explained 77.1% of the variance in their academic performance, according to the coefficient of determination (r^2) value of .771. Thus, it was determined that among Social Studies students attending Delta State's postsecondary institutions, there is a positive correlation between location, drug addiction, and academic performance.

Hypothesis 1

Drug abuse does not significantly correlate with academic performance of Social Studies students in tertiary institutions in Delta State.

Table 4: Linear Regression Analysis of drug abuse and academic performance

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	19799.021	1	19799.021	544.330	.000 ^b
	Residual	13021.601	246	36.373		
	Total	32820.622	248			

Table 4 shows a linear regression analysis of the relationship between drug abuse and academic performance of Social Studies Students at tertiary institutions in Delta State. The computed F-value of 544.330 has a p-value of 0.000. Testing the null hypothesis at an alpha level of 0.05, the p-value of 0.000 was less than the alpha level of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. As a result, drug abuse significantly correlates with academic performance of Social Studies students in tertiary institutions in Delta State.

Hypothesis 2

Drug abuse does not significantly correlate with academic performance of Social Studies students in tertiary institutions in Delta State with regard to gender.

Table 5: Multiple Regression Analysis of Gender, Drug abuse, and Academic performance

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	27909.058	2	5581.812	402.308	.000 ^b
	Residual	4911.564	244	13.874		
	Total	32820.622	248			

Table 5 shows multiple regression analysis of the relationship among gender, drug abuse, and academic performance of Social Studies Students of tertiary institution in Delta State. The computed F-value of 402.308 has a p-value of 0.000. Testing the null hypothesis at an alpha level of 0.05, the p-value of 0.000 was less than the alpha level of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. The study showed drug abuse significantly correlates with academic performance of Social Studies students in tertiary institutions in Delta State related to gender.

Hypothesis 3

Drug abuse does not significantly correlate with academic performance of Social Studies students in tertiary institutions in Delta State with regard to location.

Table 6: Multiple Regression Analysis of drug abuse and academic performance based on location

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	21343.515	2	40.505	76.280	.000 ^b
	Residual	33923.287	244	.531		
	Total	31104.802	248			

Table 6 shows a multiple regression analysis of the relationship among location, drug abuse and academic performance of Social Studies Students of tertiary institutions in Delta State. The calculated $F = 76.280$, with $df (3, 364)$ and p -value of 0.000 . The p -value is less than 0.05 level of significance. Thus the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship among location, drug abuse and academic performance of Social Studies Students of tertiary institutions in Delta State was therefore rejected. This indicates that Drug abuse significantly correlate with academic performance of Social Studies students in tertiary institutions in Delta State with regard to location,

Discussion of Results

The findings made from data analysis in line with the research questions and hypotheses formulated for this study were discussed under the following subheadings.

Drug abuse influences academic performance of Social Studies Students in tertiary institutions in Delta State

The first finding in this study revealed Drug abuse significantly correlate with academic performance of Social Studies students in tertiary institutions in Delta State. This discovery might have many explanations, one of them being that drug use by students affects their academic performance.

It can lead to decreased interest and participation in other classroom activities, which undeniably impacts performance. Students who use drugs to a certain extent might even die while in school. This finding aligns with Ngesu (2018), who identified various factors contributing to drug use among students, including curiosity, anxiety relief, the pursuit of sexual and physical pleasures, and family history. Similarly, Dankano and Garba (2020) found that drug consumption not only affects academic performance but also undermines students' morale, physical health, and overall development. This outcome supports the comprehensive theory proposed by David, Derald, and Stanley (2019), which suggests that drug addiction can reduce an undergraduate's chances of graduating from college or securing and maintaining stable employment.

Gender and drug abuse influence academic performance of Social Studies Students of tertiary institution in Delta State

The study's second finding showed that drug abuse and gender had a substantial impact on social studies students' academic performance at Delta State's postsecondary institutions. It is also true that there are gender differences in drug use at school. According to

the survey, guys misuse drugs at a higher rate than girls. The finding indicated that females use drugs less frequently than males. This might be because boys are more prone to the negative effects of drug use at school, leading to classroom distractions. These findings align with Strom et al. (2012), who discovered that academic performance is often lower among adolescents exposed to violence and drug abuse, especially in schools with high levels of drug abuse. This result supports Aransi's (2018) theory that the impact of drug use varies by gender. However, opinions in the literature about the relationship between gender and drug misuse effects differ. While some studies suggest that females are more influenced by their peers to abuse drugs, this contrasts with Amadi and Akpelu's (2018) findings, which showed no significant relationship between drug abuse and academic achievement among students based on gender.

Location and drug abuse influence academic performance of Social Studies Students of tertiary institutions in Delta State

The third finding in this study revealed that there is a significant effect between location and drug abuse on academic performance of social studies student of tertiary institutions in Delta State. Location has a lot to contribute to student behavior either in school or at home, some student who live in a local environment easy associate with bad gangs who involve in drug abuse. The study also revealed that some students who live in a local environment involve in hawking business after school, with this some of them sees that youth who take drug and might also want to practice what they see. While those students who live in the urban area due to parental negligence or over busy with work and home activities might be careless for their children such children might also indulge in taking drug with their peer in the environment. The results are consistent with Data (2017), which states that children's first extensive socialisation occurs at home. He goes on to say that certain students may be more likely to consume drugs if they reside in a rural location as opposed to an urban one. The results also support the hypothesis put out by Kebogile et al. (2021) that drug usage differs depending on geography.

Conclusion

The findings revealed that drug abuse significantly correlates with students' academic performance in social studies drug abuse has an impact on Delta State social studies students' academic achievement. It was also determined that substance addiction and location had a beneficial impact on social studies students' academic achievement at Delta State's postsecondary institutions. In Delta State's institutions, social students' academic success is predicted by their gender and place of residence (location).

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, these recommendations were made;

1. The Ministry of Education should provide more training for teachers in the area of behaviour management.
2. This training should be broad-based and a shift away from the adhoc sessions conducted by the National Centre for Education Resource Development, and
3. School administrators should also be trained in order to equip them with relevant knowledge and skills to deal with mass disruption in their schools.

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